

BROMINATION OF COMPOUNDS CONTAINING TWO AROMATIC NUCLEI. PART IV. BROMINATION OF ARYL ESTERS OF 2-NAPHTHOIC ACID

BY GANPATRAO VISHRAMRAO JADHAV AND MAHOMAD ASLAM

Bromination of phenyl, *o*-, *m*-, *p*-cresyl, *o*-, *m*-, *p*-nitrophenyl, α -, β -naphthyl, *p*-bromophenyl and 4-bromo-*o*-cresyl esters of 2-naphthoic acid is described. In the case of phenyl, *o*- and *p*-cresyl esters only 5-bromo-2-naphthoic acid could be isolated, whilst in the case of α -, β -naphthyl, and *o*-, *m*-cresyl esters, bromine enters the phenolic part of the molecule, and in the case of the rest it enters the acidic part. The constitution of the brominated esters has been proved by hydrolysis and confirmed by mixed melting point.

The present work was taken up with a view to studying the reactivity of naphthalene ring in the aryl esters of 2-naphthoic acid in bromination as compared with the benzene ring in the aryl esters of benzoic acid. It was observed by Jadhav and Rangwala (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1935, 12, 89) that bromination of simple aryl esters of benzoic acid could give better yields in presence of fuming nitric acid and that bromine entered the phenolic part, whilst in the case of nitrophenyl esters, bromination could be effected only in presence of fuming nitric acid and then too, bromine was found to enter the acidic part.

In the present work bromination of phenyl, *o*-, *m*-, *p*-cresyl, *o*-, *m*-, *p*-nitrophenyl, α -, β -naphthyl, *p*-bromophenyl and 4-bromo-*o*-cresyl esters of 2-naphthoic acid has been carried out in acetic acid medium. In the case of α - and β -naphthyl esters only, bromination takes place at room temperature and bromo derivatives with bromine in the phenolic part are obtained. Similar bromo derivative is obtained in the case of *m*-cresyl ester, but the reaction has to be carried out at boiling water-bath temperature.

In the case of phenyl, *o*- and *p*-cresyl 2-naphthoates, the bromination takes place at the boiling water-bath temperature, that too if the amount of acetic acid is just a little less than that required for complete dissolution of the ester. The brominated product is 5-bromo-2-naphthoic acid as confirmed by analysis and mixed melting point. It seems that bromination first takes place and the hydrobromic acid formed in the reaction hydrolyses the bromo-esters. To prove this, first the action of hydrobromic acid has been tried on the original esters under the same experimental conditions and they could be recovered unchanged. Afterwards the same esters of 5-bromo-2-naphthoic acid are treated with hydrobromic acid under the same experimental conditions, when hydrolysis is found to take place and 5-bromo-2-naphthoic acid is obtained.

In the case of *o*-, *m*- and *p*-nitrophenyl esters, the presence of nitro group in the phenolic part of the molecule deactivates it, but bromine could still enter the acidic part and give stable nitrophenyl esters of 5-bromo-2-naphthoic acid at the temperature of the boiling water-bath. Similarly in the case of *p*-bromophenyl 2-naphthoate and 4-bromo-*o*-cresyl 2-naphthoate, bromination at boiling water-bath temperature could give the corresponding esters of 5-bromo-2-naphthoic acid.

Bromination of *m*-cresyl 2-naphthoate with excess of bromine at the boiling water-bath temperature gives a dibromo derivative, 4-bromo-*m*-cresyl 5-bromo-2-naphthoate.

The constitutions of these bromination products has been proved by their hydrolysis except in the case of 4-bromophenyl and 4-bromo-*m*-cresyl 2-naphthoates and confirmed by mixed melting points with genuine samples prepared by the condensation of 5-bromo-2-naphthoic acid with the respective phenol.

EXPERIMENTAL

The ester was suspended in glacial acetic acid, liquid bromine was gradually added to it and the mixture was heated on a boiling water-bath for the required period. On cooling the reaction mixture, a solid separated which was crystallised from acetic acid. The compounds are described in Table I.

TABLE I

N indicates naphthoate.

Ester (4.g. each)	Br ₂ .	Acetic acid	Hours.	Name of product.	M.p.	Bromine.	
						Formula.	Found. Calc.
Phenyl 2-N	3 g.	35 c.c.	4	5-Bromo-2-naphthoic acid	263-64°	C ₁₁ H ₇ O ₂ Br	31.7 31.9
<i>o</i> -Cresyl 2-N	4	35	5	5-Bromo-2-naphthoic acid	263-64°	C ₁₁ H ₇ O ₂ Br	31.5 31.9
<i>m</i> -Cresyl 2-N	2.5	35	3	4-Bromo- <i>m</i> -cresyl 2-N	127-28°	C ₁₅ H ₁₃ O ₂ Br	23.4 23.5
<i>p</i> -Cresyl 2-N	3	35	6	5-Bromo-2-naphthoic acid	263-64°	C ₁₁ H ₇ O ₂ NBr	32.2 31.9
<i>o</i> -Nitrophenyl 2-N	6.5	50	3	<i>o</i> -Nitrophenyl 5-bromo-2-N	167-68°	C ₁₇ H ₁₀ O ₄ NBr	21.6 21.5
<i>m</i> -Nitrophenyl 2-N	3.5	50	3	<i>m</i> -Nitrophenyl 5-bromo-2-N	172-73°	C ₁₇ H ₁₀ O ₄ NBr	21.5 21.5
<i>p</i> -Nitrophenyl 2-N	3.5	50	3	<i>p</i> -Nitrophenyl 5-bromo-2-N	200-1°	C ₁₇ H ₁₀ O ₄ Br	21.8 21.5
1-Naphthyl 2-N	2.5	50	2*	4-Bromo-1-naphthyl 2-N	151-52°	C ₂₁ H ₁₅ O ₂ Br	21.4 21.2
2-Naphthyl 2-N	2.5	70	24*	1-Bromo-2-naphthyl 2-N	164-65°	C ₂₁ H ₁₅ O ₂ Br	21.1 21.1
<i>m</i> -Cresyl 2-N	7	40	5	4-bromo- <i>m</i> -cresyl 5-bromo-2-N	147-48°	C ₁₈ H ₁₃ O ₂ Br ₂	37.7 38.1
4-Bromophenyl 2-N	2.5	40	3	4-Bromophenyl 5-bromo-2-N	143-44°	C ₁₇ H ₁₀ O ₂ Br ₂	39.1 39.4
4-Bromo- <i>o</i> -cresyl 2-N	2.5	40	4	4-Bromo- <i>o</i> -cresyl 5-bromo-2-N	136-37°	C ₁₈ H ₁₃ O ₂ Br ₂	37.6 38.1

* The reaction mixture was left at room temperature.

Hydrolysis.—The bromo-esters were boiled for 4-5 hours under reflux with 7-8% sodium hydroxide solution in presence of a little alcohol. Carbon dioxide was then passed through the solution, except in the case of *o*-nitrophenyl 5-bromo-2-naphthoate, in which case the phenol was separated by steam distillation, when the phenolic component separated was extracted with ether and the phenol was confirmed by mixed melting point. The solution left after the removal of phenol gave on acidification 5-bromo-2-naphthoic acid, confirmed by mixed point.